

THROUGH THICKNESS REINFORCED COMPOSITE/METAL JOINTS – THE IMPACT OF THE PINNING TECHNOLOGY ON THE JOINT'S TENSILE STRENGTH

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Keywords: Through thickness reinforcement, Pinning, Tensile testing, RTM, Composite/Metal joint

ABSTRACT

Through thickness reinforced composite/metal joints represent a novel approach for lightweight hybrid joint design. Small fasteners, called pins, penetrate the composite material and create a fiber friendly form fit between the composite and metallic joint partner. Pins can be created by different technologies and various studies have been conducted to analyze each individual pinning technology. However, the test results of the different technologies are difficult to compare due to a variation in specimen design, specimen production and the testing methods.

This paper presents an experimental study on quasistatic testing of pinned composite/steel joints. The pinning technologies that were selected were laser pinning, comparable to Surf Sculpt, inserted pins and pins created by a welding process, called Cold Metal Transfer (CMT). This study focuses primarily on tensile strength and joint failure modes. The specimens were produced using a closed mold RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) process to ensure uniform laminate quality for all specimens. The importance of shear strength and bending stiffness of the pins is demonstrated by analysis of local strain behavior and failure modes by the help of Digital Image Correlation techniques.

1 INTRODUCTION

Modern lightweight structures for aerospace and automotive applications often consist of a mix of several materials. Specifically, the combination of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) and metals help to meet the requirements of high stiffness and ultimate strength, combined with great tolerance to impact loads.

Conventionally, CFRP and metals are joined by adhesive bonding or by form fit methods like riveting or bolting. Both joining methods have been extensively researched and used for decades.

Adhesive bonding represents a fiber friendly joining technology. The joint design, specifically the overlap length, choice of adherent thickness, joint-end configuration and fiber orientation has shown to have a high impact on the joint's mechanical performance [1]. The surface-pretreatment is also of high importance for the mechanical performance of the adhesive joint [2, 3]. However, adhesive joints have to be sealed in order to prevent damage by aggressive media. Another disadvantage is spontaneous failure behavior. The introduction of "safety rivets" helps to alleviate these drawbacks, but substantially increases the weight of the joint.

The mechanical behavior of bolted and riveted joints has extensively been investigated [4]. They can be disassembled and are comparably easy to produce. However, destruction of fibers through borehole drilling leads to weakening of the CFRP adherents. Due to its anisotropic material behavior, stress concentrations around bearing holes are more critical for CFRP materials in comparison to isotropic materials like metals. These disadvantages are overcome by local thickening of the CFRP joint partners which leads to an increased weight input.

The pinning technology was invented with the goal to minimize the disadvantages of the conventional methods mentioned above. Pinned hybrid composite/metal joints are insitu-bonded. No

borehole drilling is necessary as the fasteners, small pins, are pushed into the dry fibers prior to resin injection.

Pins can be created by using several technologies. Experimental testing has been conducted with Comeld™ joints [5] by applying Surfi-Sculpt™ technology [6], comparable to laser-pinning technology (see chapter 2.1). Tensile testing for bolted co-cured GFRP/aluminum (glass-fiber reinforced plastic) joints, comparable to inserted pinning technology, has been performed [7] as well as for CFRP/steel pinned joints produced with the help of CMT-welding technology (see chapter 2.3) [8]. Numerical optimization of pinned hybrid joints has been investigated by several authors [9, 10]. However, due to the use of different materials, testing methods and joint geometries, the above mentioned pinning technologies cannot directly be compared by analyzing these studies. The goal of this study is to compare laser-pinned specimens with inserted pinned specimens and CMT-pinned specimens in terms of maximum tensile load, failure mechanics and energy dissipation capacity.

2 CREATION OF PINS

2.1 Laser - pinning

Laser-generated pins were produced by applying a technology comparable to Surfi-Sculpt™, developed at The Welding Institute (TWI). An electron beam is deflected over a surface and creates an array of protrusions and intrusions through local melting of the base material [6]. Instead of an electron beam, for this study, a 3 kW single-mode fiber laser at a wavelength of $\lambda=1070$ nm was used. The beam was focused on the workpiece by a scanning optics. The focus diameter of the laser beam was $d_{86\%}=48$ μm , the rayleigh length $z_R=1.1$ mm and the resulting beam parameter product $BPP=0.5$ mm*mrad. The principal procedure is described in [11].

2.2 Inserted pinning

Metallic sheets with inserted pins were manufactured by drilling holes of a diameter of 1.5 mm into the metal. Subsequently, cylindrical spring steel pins of 10 mm length were inserted into the holes. A press fit connection held the pins in place.

2.3 CMT – pinning

Cold-metal transfer (CMT) is an arc-welding process invented by Fronius [12]. Pins are created by welding a wire onto a metallic surface. High currents cause tearing of the wire at a certain height. Due to the usage of automatic pulsed activation and deactivation of the heating arc, CMT welding generates significantly lower heat input compared to conventional MIG welding processes. The lower heat input results in a small heat affected zone and besides these small zones, the base material is not weakened by the welding process.

Pinned metallic sheets produced with the technologies mentioned above are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Creation of pins: Laser (left), Inserted (center), CMT (right)

3 PRODUCTION OF SPECIMENS

3.1 Materials

The tensile test specimens were produced using Toho/Tenax IMS65 fibers, 0/0/90 non-crimp-fabric (NCF), a toughened thermoset RTM resin and stainless steel inserts (AISI 304). Transversal isotropy

was assumed for each composite ply according to the fiber (1) direction. The pins for the inserted pinning configuration were made of spring steel (DIN EN 10270-1) due to its high yield strength and tensile strength. As the laser pinning process and CMT process set the pin material to be similar to the raw material, pins for the corresponding configurations were made of stainless steel. The most important mechanical properties of CFRP and metallic joint partner as well as for the spring steel pins for inserted pinned specimens are listed in Table 1.

Material	E_1 [GPa]	E_3 [GPa]	G_{12} [GPa]	G_{23} [GPa]	ν_{12} [-]	ν_{23} [-]
0°-ply (IMS65/Resin RTM)	167	9.5	4.5	3.65	0.3	0.3
Steel 304 DIN EN 10020	210	210	80.769	80.769	0.3	0.3
Spring steel SH DIN EN 10270-1	206	206	81.423	81.432	0.26	0.26

Table 1: Material properties

3.2 Design of specimens

The tensile test standard ASTM D3528-96 for hybrid composite/metal double-lap adhesive joints was selected for the comparison of pinned joints to adhesive joints as well as pinned joints to pinned joints themselves. Light geometric modifications of this standard were necessary, refer to Figure 2. The joint was chosen to be 11 mm in height to account for the maximum pin height of 3.5 mm, deviating from the standard which sets the joint height to 6.4 mm. In order to reduce free edge stresses for the adhesive bond, a taper of 30° was applied.

Figure 2: Design of specimens

3.3 Preforming, RTM-process and cutting

The layup was chosen to be symmetrical to the mid-plane and near quasiisotropic using 0°, 90° and ±45° plies, a total of 60 plies (20 NCF-layers). By using thermoplastic binder material for improved handling characteristics, three preform stacks were manufactured, labelled section 1 through section 3. Section 3 and section 2 were positioned in an RTM-mold first, followed by the metallic insert. Subsequently, section 1 was placed on top of section 2 and the metallic insert, see Figure 3.

The RTM-tool consists of two steel molds mounted on a heatable RTM-press. By closing the heated tool with a force of 750 kN, the pins were stamped into the preform, followed by the resin injection at a temperature of 165° C. The cure time was set to 120 min at 190° C.

Figure 3: In-situ joining process

Demolding took place after cool down of the RTM-setup at a temperature of 60° C. Utilizing the process explained above, RTM-panels shown in Figure 4 were produced and thirteen single test specimens were cut from one panel using a waterjet-cutting machine.

Figure 4: RTM-Panel

3.4 Setup for tensile specimens

The adhesive reference joint was produced using a flat metallic insert without pins. The surface of the metallic sheet was roughened with sandpaper grit 80 and cleaned with isopropanol prior to joining. In the RTM-process, the joint was co-bonded using the RTM-resin as an adhesive between the composite and metallic joint partner. A defined adhesive thickness was not adjusted.

The basic pin adjustment for the pinned specimens was 7 pins in x-direction and 5 pins in y-direction, equally distributed on both sides of the metallic insert. The laser pins were cone-shaped, the pin root diameter was set to a maximum possible value of 1.9 mm, while the pin height was 2.7 mm. After the pin manufacturing process, the surface was cleaned with a steel brush.

For the inserted pins, holes of 1.5 mm diameter were drilled in the metallic sheet followed by the insertion of pins of 10 mm length, leading to a pin height of 3.5 mm on both sides by taking into account the thickness of the metallic insert (3 mm). Two different pin adjustments were used for the inserted pinning technology – the basic 7x5 pattern, named “Inserted 1” and an alternative pattern consisting of 2 pins in the first row, 3 pins in the second row, 4 pins in the third row and 5 pins in row 4 to 7. Both adjustments are shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Pin adjustment: 7x5 (left), 1x2;1x3;1x4;4x5 (right)

Due to limitations of the CMT-welding process, the pin diameter was chosen to be 1.2 mm and 1.6 mm. As a result of the welding process, the root diameter exceeds the pin wire diameter by a factor of 2 to 2.5, leading to an increased shear area. In contrast to the setups “Laser”, “Inserted 1” as well as “Inserted 2”, CMT-pinned metallic sheets had to be sandblasted in order to remove welding waste.

All pinned metallic sheets were cleaned with isopropanol prior to resin injection to remove contamination on the metallic surface and pins. The setup for all of the pinned specimens is listed in Table 2.

Joint type	Pin adjustment	Pin shape	Pin root diameter	Pin wire diameter	Pin height	Pin material	Specimens tested
	[-]	[-]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[-]	[-]
Adhesive	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
Laser	7x5	cone-shaped	1.9	Varying	2.7	Steel	5
Inserted 1	7x5	cylindrical	1.5	1.5	3.5	Spring steel	2
Inserted 2	1x2;1x3; 1x4;4x5	cylindrical	1.5	1.5	3.5	Spring steel	4
CMT 1	7x5	cylindrical	2.5 - 2.9	1.2	3.5	Steel	6
CMT 2	7x5	cylindrical	3.3 - 3.9	1.6	3.5	Steel	5

Table 2: Setup for pinned specimens

4 TESTING PROCEDURE

4.1 Testing setup

The quasistatic testing was performed using an electro-mechanical universal testing machine (UTM) with a maximum load range of 250 kN. According to standard ASTM D3528-96D, the crosshead speed was set to 1.3 mm/min. First concept tests showed that additional test grips for specimen fixation between the holding jaws are not necessary as the original specimen surface provides sufficient grip for the estimated maximum loads. The specimens were clamped vertically with the lateral surface pointing towards the spectator’s position, see Figure 6.

Figure 6: Tensile test setup

4.2 Measurement of stress and strain

The applied load was measured by the UTM's internal load cell whereas the displacement was quantified with the help of a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system of type "GOM Aramis-4M". Therefore, prior to testing, one of the lateral surfaces had to be covered with a random black-on-white speckle pattern. A 3D-measurement system was used, involving two cameras to measure displacement in x-, z- and y-directions.

A normalized stress value σ_{norm} was defined in order to directly compare the specimen's tensile stress to the tensile strength of the metallic joint partner. Therefore, σ_{norm} is calculated by dividing the tensile load by the cross section of the metallic tab.

$$\sigma_{norm} = \frac{F_x}{w_m * t_m} \quad (1)$$

where F_x represents the tensile load in x-direction, w_m and t_m describe the metallic tab's initial width and thickness, prior to tensile testing, thus necking of the metallic tab. According to equation (1) the average shear strength for all test specimens of one setup will be defined as $\bar{\sigma}_{norm}max$.

To measure the strain ϵ_{norm} , a virtual video-extensometer was utilized by using the Aramis data. Therefore, the displacements along two characteristic lines in z-direction were measured. The first line was chosen to be located at the edge of the taper of the CFRP joint partner, whereas the second line was chosen to be located behind the joining area with an initial distance of 50 mm to line 1, see Figure 6 above. As the DIC-system measures several displacement values along these lines, the mean value was used. These two positions ensure that the distribution of displacement in x-direction is close to uniform along the lines. ϵ_{norm} can be calculated by dividing the current distance between line 1 and line 2 by the initial distance.

$$\epsilon_{norm} = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{L_0} - 1 \quad (2)$$

where \bar{x}_1 and \bar{x}_2 represent the current average positions of line 1 and line 2 and L_0 describes the initial distance. DIC was used for all specimens with the exception of setup "Inserted 1".

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Maximum stress and failure mode

Test results for normalized tensile strength of all setups are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Comparison of average normalized tensile strength $\bar{\sigma}_{norm}max$ for different specimen setups

The adhesive reference joint failed at a mean value of 366.13 MPa with a standard deviation of 3.62 MPa. The average shear strength between metal and CFRP joint partner can be calculated to $\bar{\tau}_{adhesive} = 13.87$ MPa.

Laser pinned joints were able to withstand normalized tensile stresses 27.4% higher than those of the adhesive reference with a mean value of 466.43 MPa and a standard variation of 6.23 MPa. Bending of the pins lead to a force deflection and opening behaviour of the CFRP laminate and finally, to delamination of the CFRP laminate.

The test specimens with setup “Inserted 1” failed due to tensile failure of the metallic tab at a mean value of 518.36 MPa. This was caused by reduced cross section and notch effects along the first pinned row. In order to reduce these notch effects, setup “Inserted 2” was defined.

The failure mode for setup “Inserted 2” was detected to be bending of the pins, resulting in delamination failure of the CFRP laminate at a mean value of 559.85 MPa and a standard variation of 11.11 MPa.

An improvement of 53.0% to the adhesive reference was obtained by CMT-pinned specimens with a pin diameter of 1.2 mm, named “CMT 1”. The average normalized tensile strength $\bar{\sigma}_{norm}max$ was measured to 559.99 MPa. The standard deviation was found to be more than doubled compared to the previous setup “Inserted 2” with a value of 25.10 MPa. Bending of pins, delamination in the CFRP and also sporadic shearing at the pin root was identified to be the failure mode for this setup.

Highest σ_{norm} values were observed for CMT-pinned specimens with a diameter of 1.6 mm, namely “CMT 2”. The average normalized tensile strength was 605.85 MPa with a standard variation of 17.43 MPa. Compared to the adhesive reference joint, an improvement of 65.5% in tensile strength could be achieved with this setup. Similar to setup “CMT 1”, joints failed due to bending of pins, delamination in the CFRP and sporadic shearing at the pin root. Failure modes for the different specimen setups are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Failure modes for pinned setups

5.2 Stress-strain behavior

An analysis of the stress-strain curve of each setup helps to understand the mechanical behavior of the pinned specimens. Figure 9 displays the $\sigma_{\text{norm}}-\varepsilon_{\text{norm}}$ relation of representative specimens of all the setups tested with the help of DIC. A comparison of linear elastic behavior for the different setups indicates that for laser pinned specimens as well as for CMT-pinned specimens, the initial stiffness is almost identical to the adhesive reference joint. The presence of drilled holes in setup “Inserted 2”

leads to premature plastic deformation of the metallic tab, hence significant degradation of the overall joint stiffness. Poor bending stiffness of the laser pins is responsible for flattening of the stress-strain curve and sudden failure at $\epsilon_{norm} = 0.06$.

The spring steel pins of setup “Inserted 2” provide very good bending stiffness and shear strength. Stress-strain behavior therefore is highly dominated by the deformation of the metallic tab. Deviating from other setups, these specimens showed gradual failure. After bending of the pins in row 1, the remaining pins are still able to provide sufficient bending stiffness to prevent sudden failure of the entire joint. Slow opening of the CFRP laminate and a step by step degradation of normalized tensile stress could be observed, resulting in ultimate failure due to delamination between single composite layers. Hybrid joints of setup “Inserted 2” were able to withstand the highest normalized strains up to $\epsilon_{norm} = 0.12$ to 0.17.

CMT-pinned specimens of setup “CMT 1” and “CMT 2” showed related stress-strain behavior, high initial joint stiffness as well as high tensile strength. Specimens with CMT-pins of 1.2 mm diameter (“CMT 1”) failed at normalized strains of $\epsilon_{norm} = 0.08$ to 0.13, while specimens of setup “CMT 2” were able to withstand strains of $\epsilon_{norm} = 0.075$ to 0.12.

Figure 9: Stress-strain relation for different setups

Local dissipated energy capacity E_{diss} of the joint area can be analyzed by taking into account normalized tensile strain, normalized tensile stress, initial distance as well as the metallic tab’s initial width and thickness.

$$E_{diss} = \left(\int_0^{\epsilon_{norm,max}} \sigma_{norm}(\epsilon_{norm}) d\epsilon_{norm} \right) * w_m * t_m * L_0 \quad (3)$$

Specimens of setup “Laser” are able to dissipate about 9.2 times as much energy as the adhesive reference joint. CMT-pinned specimens exceed the adhesive reference joint by a factor of 13.5 (“CMT 1”) up to 17.3 (“CMT 2”). Due to high plastic deformation of the metallic joint partner, specimens of setup “Inserted 2” are even able to dissipate 23.6 times more energy compared to the reference joint.

Figure 10 below shows DIC measurements for displacement in x-direction for an exemplary specimen of setup “CMT 2” at different load levels. Extensive plastic deformation of the metallic joint partner can be seen, as well as high stiffness of the composite joint partner behind the joining area. After failure of the adhesive bond (at $\sigma_{norm} = 0.6 * \sigma_{norm,max}$), high deviation of displacement in x-direction along the specimen’s thickness (z-direction) can be observed. Once the adhesive bond has failed, pins are exclusively responsible for load transfer. High shear strength and bending stiffness of the pins are essential in order to reach high tensile strength for hybrid pinned joints. Both parameters

can be adjusted by an adequate selection of pin material and pin geometry. However, pin diameter cannot be increased to very high values as degradation of mechanical properties of the CFRP joint partner are dependent on fiber undulation. High pin diameters cause high fiber undulations, therefore a trade-off between pin diameter and degradation of mechanical properties of the CFRP joint member has to be made. For pinned composite to composite joints, several authors [13, 14, 15] state pin densities of 0.5% to 4.9%. In these studies, pin densities for composite/steel hybrid joints were 2.9% (“Laser”) up to 12.0% (“CMT 2”).

Figure 10: Analysis of displacement in x-direction at several load states, using DIC. Setup: CMT 2

6 CONCLUSION

An analysis of the different setup’s test results indicate that pinned hybrid CFRP/steel double-lap joints are able to increase the joint’s tensile strength and strain, compared to adhesive co-bonded joints. The strongest results in terms of tensile strength were measured for CMT-pinned specimens with a pin diameter of 1.6 mm. Pinned specimens with inserted pins achieved the highest strains and energy absorption capacities.

The main failure mode was found to be the opening of the CFRP joint partner, with the exception of setup “Inserted 1” which failed due to tensile failure of the metallic joint partner, caused by notch effects. Furthermore, it was found that bending stiffness and shear strength of pins have a high impact on the joint’s tensile strength. Limitations on the pin diameter, which mainly influence the bending stiffness and strength of the pins, are set by the degradation of mechanical properties of the CFRP joint partner due to fiber undulations. Also, stamping the pins into the preform becomes more difficult with high pin diameters.

State-of-the-art surface preparation methods for composite/metal joints should be taken into consideration for the adhesive reference as well as for pinned joints. FEA-models can be validated by DIC-testing results. Optimization of the geometry in terms of pin shape and distribution as well as the thickness of the adherents will further improve the joint’s mechanical properties. The analysis of the fiber deflection and measurement of the resulting degradation of mechanical properties for high pin

diameters is a major challenge. In order to validate the pinning technology for industrial applications, extensive fatigue testing has to be performed in future studies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

GE aviation US, GE Global Research Centre Munich Composite Manufacturing Laboratory and GE Global Research Centre Niskayuna are gratefully acknowledged for their funding and technical support. The authors also acknowledge the institute for machine tools and Industrial Management (IWB) at Technical University Munich as well as AIT/LKR Leichtmetallkompetenzzentrum Ranshofen for their support regarding Laser pin technology and CMT-pin technology.

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